

Recommended citation: Martin, D. A., Conlon, E., & Bowe, B. (2019). Engineering education, split between two cultures: an examination into patterns of implementation of ethics education in engineering programmes in Ireland. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 1742-1752). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14657091.

Engineering Education, Split Between Two Cultures: An Examination into Patterns of Implementation of Ethics Education

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Conference Key Areas: Gender, Inclusion and Ethics

Keywords: engineering culture; ethics education; nontechnical skills; delivery methods; accreditation

ABSTRACT

International literature points to the unevenness of ethics education in countries where ethics is an accreditation criterion for engineering programmes ([3], [8], [21]), and a low presence in countries where ethics doesn't feature as an accreditation criteria [20].

Given that most research carried on the implementation of engineering ethics education is based in US, our contribution aims to fill a gap by providing insights into the implementation of ethics education in the European context. The study enquires how ethics is implemented in engineering programmes in Ireland, where ethics is an accreditation criterion since 2007 [10]. The research is supported by the national accreditation body and the sample consists of 23 engineering programmes in Ireland. The method employed is a simple statistical analysis based on a rubric present in the documentation submitted for accreditation, in which programmes are required to self-assess how each accreditation outcome is being met.

The findings reveal that nontechnical outcomes have the lowest weight in the curricula of engineering programmes, with ethics having the lowest presence of all accreditation outcomes according to the programmes' self-assessment. These findings show the prevalence of an engineering education model focused on the development of technical skills. There are also disciplinary differences in the provision of ethics education, with programmes of electric, electronic and computer engineering attributing a lower weight to ethics and other nontechnical outcomes compared with other engineering disciplines.

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1 BACKGROUND

Ethical concerns are a recent addition to engineering programmes. Traditionally, disciplines of exact sciences such as engineering were regarded as morally neutral, and henceforth did not require ethical instruction [9]. Looking at the history of engineering education and current trends, three paradigms of engineering professional identity emerge [14]. These represent three competing visions about the nature of the engineering profession, as well as about the educational approaches to support them.

First, there is the academic vision of engineering as applied science, dominant in science universities. Second, a market-driven vision of engineering as technological innovation, present in an entrepreneurial university model. Thirdly, we have the integrative vision of engineering as public service, promoted by an ecological oriented university. Describing the later approach, ([14], p.264) notes that it mixes elements of both the academic and market driven models into a “socially oriented hybrid” that favours an educational approach which includes the scientific, technical, ethical, social and environmental dimensions of engineering. They also state that this mode of engineering education has played a less prominent role historically.

Currently, there is an increased presence of ethics education in national accreditation systems of engineering programmes worldwide, following the introduction of the Washington Accord [7]. The Washington Accord places a strong emphasis on the ethical and social responsibilities of engineers, stating that graduates are expected to “understand and commit to professional ethics and responsibilities and norms of engineering practice,” as well as to “understand and evaluate the sustainability and impact of professional engineering work in the solution of complex engineering problems in societal and environmental contexts” and “apply reasoning informed by contextual knowledge to assess of the societal, health, safety, legal and cultural issues and the consequent responsibilities relevant to engineering practice and solutions to complex engineering problems” [13]. Nevertheless, the current state of engineering ethics education points to an uneven presence in countries where ethics is an accreditation criterion for engineering programmes ([3]; [8]; [21]). There is also a significant disparity between the perceived importance of ethical and societal related practices by engineering faculty and their actual presence in the curriculum of engineering programmes ([22], p.14).

In Portugal, where ethics education does not feature as an accreditation criterion for engineering degree programs, 60% of the courses did not provide any mandatory or optional ethics units in their curriculum [20]. [19] puts this situation down to the strong influence of the lecturer in shaping curriculum development, combined with a reduced ethical training of engineering lecturers. She notes that “almost all engineering teachers had made an academic career that didn't include any curricular explicit form of ethics education.” This finding is consistent with empirical research carried in US ([3]; [11]; [15]; [27]; [28]) and Australia ([24], p.136), which revealed that ethics had a low presence in the curriculum of engineering programmes prior to the introduction of an ethical criterion for accreditation. Accreditation bodies can thus have a positive influence on how programmes shape their curricula in this regard, given that an ethical criterion for accreditation has been shown to lead to an increased emphasis on engineering ethics education.

The main risk associated with a weak presence of ethics education in engineering programmes is that of perpetuating a traditional view of engineering as a solely

technical discipline. With it, passing on to students the message that ethics is not as important for their education and future profession as other skills, such as technical abilities ([18], p.525). In our times marked by a rapid pace of technological development, the two cultures of science and humanities described by [25] can no longer exist separately and on different hierarchical levels.

[6] warns about the dangers of separating the “two cultures” in engineering education. She observed a correlation between the emphasis placed by a programme on ethical and social issues and students’ concern for their ethical and social responsibilities as engineers. Students from engineering programs that favour the development of technical skills to the detriment of ethics and social engagement tend to have declining beliefs about the importance of public welfare from their first to their last year of studies. ([1], p.58) also found that as engineering students advance in their study programme, they tend to develop strong and rigid views about the lower value of academic disciplines oriented towards people and society. A survey about the views on ethics held by students upon entering their engineering degrees show that almost a third of the 1136 first year engineering students interviewed did not believe that engineers act ethically and it was not realistic to expect engineers to have an ethical behaviour [26]. Engineering students are also found to express significantly lower commitment to social activism and concern for society than students from other disciplines ([2]; [23]). What is worse, [6] notes, engineering students’ engagement with public welfare issues does not rebound upon graduating and entering the workforce.

University education is the propitious period when engineering students start to develop their identities as future professionals [17]. The weight given to ethics in the engineering curricula is extremely important in sending students the message that ethics is not peripheral to engineering, but a substantial aspect of their profession [16]. As ([5], p.72) points out, teaching only the technical aspects of engineering will direct students to consider solely these once they go into the work field, without even noticing the ethical concerns embedded in their work. This further enforces [6]’s contention that “if engineering programs can overcome forces of isomorphism [...] they could produce a new brand of engineer, one that thinks critically about the construction of public welfare and the technological systems on which he/she works.” The stakes are thus high on the issue of a more important weight given to ethics in engineering programmes, on a same par with technical related learning outcomes.

Summing up, the main findings of the literature review show that the current state of engineering ethics education is characterized by a growing presence of ethics education in engineering educational systems where ethics features as an accreditation criteria, yet still a low priority given to ethics in the engineering curricula. Notable is also the correlation between the emphasis given to ethics in the curricula of engineering programmes and the formation of students’ professional identity as socially responsible engineers.

2 METHOD

The main research question of the paper is what are the patterns in regards to the weight given to ethics in Engineering Honours Programmes in Ireland? To answer this question, we use a quantitative simple statistical analysis of the documents submitted for accreditation by participant Engineering programmes. The method is employed to determine the presence of ethics related outcomes in the engineering curricula

according to the programmes' own assessment of how they meet each of the seven accreditation outcomes.

The analysis is based on a rubric present in each document submitted by Engineering programmes in Ireland for accreditation. In this rubric, programmes are asked to self-assess how each of their modules meets the seven accreditation outcomes presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Programme outcomes for accreditation of Engineering programmes in Ireland

Programme outcome	Domain
a	Knowledge and understanding of the mathematics, sciences, engineering sciences and technologies underpinning their branch of engineering
b	The ability to identify, formulate, analyse and solve engineering problems
c	The ability to design a system
d	The ability to design and conduct experiments and to conduct guided research
e	An understanding of the need for high ethical standards in the practice of engineering, including the responsibilities towards people and the environment
f	The ability to work effectively as an individual, in teams and in multidisciplinary settings, together with the capacity to undertake lifelong learning
g	The ability to communicate effectively on specialised engineering activities with the engineering community and with society at large

The self-assessment scale recommended by the accreditation body contains 5 scores ranging from 0 to 4. These are known as POLO scores and their meaning is described in Table 2. The programmes have to assigning a scoring for each of their modules, based on the learning outcomes achieved by the module. Typically, this self-assessment process is carried by the module's coordinator(s), as specified in the documents submitted for accreditation by seven programmes.

Table 2. Five-point POLO scale for module contribution to programme outcomes

Score	Description
4	Module strongly contributes with a large component of assessment relating to the Programme Outcome.
3	Fairly strong contribution, with significant assessment relating to the Programme Outcome.
2	Some assessment relating to Programme Outcome, but the Programme Outcome is not a central theme of the module.
1	Only a small portion of assessment relates to the Programme Outcome.
0	Module does not contribute to the Programme Outcome.

Ireland has a two-tiered system of engineering education, divided into universities and institutes of technology. Programmes offered by both institutions types were included in the current study: 15 programmes offered by universities and 8 programmes offered

by institutes of technology. In total, 7 institutions participated: 5 universities and 2 institutions of technology. One institution of university type whose programmes underwent accreditation in the period under analysis declined to participate. The programmes comprise a wide range of engineering disciplines, as seen in *Table 3*. This allows the researcher to analyse different disciplinary contexts of engineering ethics education.

Table 3. Participant Engineering programmes disciplines

University programmes	Institute of Technology programmes
Electronic and Computer Engineering (2)	Electronic Engineering (1)
Electrical and Electronic Engineering (2)	Manufacturing and Design (1)
Electrical Engineering (1)	Building Services Engineering (1)
Electronic Engineering (1)	Structural Engineering (1)
Computer Science and Information Technology (1)	Civil Engineering (1)
Civil, Structural and Environmental (1)	Energy Systems Engineering (1)
Civil Engineering (2)	Mechanical Engineering (2)
Energy Engineering (1)	
Mechanical Engineering (2)	
Process and Chemical Engineering (1)	
Biomedical Engineering (1)	

The programme averages for each of the seven learning outcomes have been calculated based on the POLO scores provided by the programmes in the documentation submitted for accreditation. Only 56% of the programmes (amounting to 13 programmes) used the scale of 0-4 recommended by the accreditation body, for the purpose of self-assessment. Although all 8 IOT used the 5 point scale recommended by Engineers Ireland, less than a quarter of the university programmes (amounting to 5 programmes) employed this scale.

The remaining 10 university programmes employed a diverse range of scales, besides the 0-4 POLO scale. Three programmes from the same university institution employed a self-assessment scale of 0-22, which the researcher uniformed as follows. The programme used a score of 1-5 to indicate “a small contribution”, which was translated into a 1. A score of 6-10 is described by the programme to indicate “some contribution”, which was translated into a 2. A score of 11-15 is described by the programme to indicate a “fairly strong contribution”, which was translated into a 3, while a score of 16-22 is described by the programme to indicate “a strong contribution”, which was then translated into a 4. The modules that received no score by the programme are understood to have no contribution to the learning outcome, a self-assessment which was translated into a 0.

Six programmes used a self-assessment scale that cannot be converted to the 0-4 scale. As such, three university programmes matched how their modules meet the seven learning outcomes by splitting the contribution of each module to the programme outcomes in terms of ECTS credits. One university programme opted for splitting the contribution of each module to the programme outcomes in terms of percentages. Finally, two university programmes used a 4 point coloured heat map to show how the modules contributed to the programme outcomes. Although the description of the four colours matched the description of the scores 1-4, no colour was assigned for modules with no contribution to the programmes outcomes, which would correspond to the score of 0 of the recommended POLO scale described in Table 2

By analyzing the average POLO scores for all seven accreditation outcomes and for all programmes, the study determines the weight given to ethics in engineering programmes according to the programmes own assessment and compare it with the average POLO scores for the other outcomes. Based on the POLO scores for the ethical outcome, the researcher calculated the percentage distribution of the five scores for the ethical outcome within each programme, in order to establish methods of delivery of ethics. It then compared the distribution of POLO scores across all programmes, in order to identify patterns in methods of delivery of ethics education. The method helped identify patterns and variations in the presence of ethics in engineering programme, according to the participant programmes' own assessment carried for the purpose of accreditation.

3 FINDINGS

According to this numerical analysis, the preliminary data reveals that the ethical outcome *e* is preponderantly self-assessed the lowest of all learning outcomes by the programmes under investigation. *Table 4* shows that the average POLO scores given by the 17 programmes to outcome *e* falls between 0.81-2.41, with an overall average of 1.56.

When comparing the average of outcome *e* to the average scores of the other six programme outcomes, the overall average for outcome *e* is the lowest. In fact, it is more than twice lower than the overall average for outcome *a* (mathematics and scientific knowledge) and outcome *b* (problem solving). For ten of the 17 programmes, accounting for 59% of the participant programmes that employed either the 0-4 self-assessment scale or a scale which can be converted to 0-4, the average for outcome *e* is more than twice lower than the average of programme outcome *a*. For one programme the average for outcome *e* is more than three times lower than the average for the highest outcome *a*.

The color gradient *Table 4* captures a striking image of the existing dichotomy between technical skills and nontechnical skills. The total average POLO scores for each outcome across the 17 programmes reveals a strong focus of engineering education on developing skills traditionally associated with the engineering profession, such as technical, mathematical and scientific knowledge, problem solving and design, which have the top average scores. On the other side, the average scores for non-technical learning outcomes e-g (ethics, teamwork, communication) are consistently self-assessed with the lowest averages.

Table 4. The weight given to the accreditation outcomes based on self assessment (n=17)

	Outcome a	Outcome b	Outcome c	Outcome d	Outcome e	Outcome f	Outcome g
IoT A Energy	3.47	3.16	2.82	2.85	2.41	2.58	2.56
IoT A Mechanical	3.69	3.67	3.22	3.33	2.37	3.11	2.9
IoT A Electronic	3.38	3.19	2.45	2.38	1.55	1.9	2.19
IoT B Build Services	3.13	3.3	2.34	1.91	1.99	1.85	2.23
IoT B Manufacturing	3.3	3.25	2.1	2	1.7	2.35	2.1
IoT B Mechanical	3.44	3.39	2.24	2.43	1.64	2.53	2.5
IoT B Structural	3.22	3.51	1.98	1.8	1.37	1.54	1.58
IoT B Civil	3.12	3.35	2.03	1.86	1.87	1.91	1.87
U C Electronic&C.S.	3.33	3.18	2.28	1.52	0.88	1.21	1.39
U D Chemical	2.36	2.19	2.05	1.15	1.05	1.51	1.34
U D Civil, Structural &Environmental	2.06	1.95	1.74	1.01	0.94	1.4	1.51
U D Energy	2.4	2.3	1.9	0.94	1	1.3	1.15
U D Electric&Electronic	2.21	2.25	1.89	0.95	0.81	1.18	1.24
U E Biomedical	3.73	3.53	2.57	2.39	1.68	2.23	2.13
U E Electronic	3.71	3.63	2.86	2.98	1.7	2.21	2.29
U E Electric	3.74	3.68	2.77	2.77	1.88	2	2.05
U E Mechanical	3.69	3.46	2.49	2.83	1.69	2.2	2.29
AVG	3.18	3.12	2.33	2.07	1.56	1.94	1.96

Analyzing disciplinary differences, *Table 4* shows that the lowest overall averages for outcome e are registered by the programmes of Electric and Electronic Engineering (average 0.81) and Electronic and Computer Science (average 0.88)

Looking at the percentage of modules self-assessed with each of the 0-4 POLO scores, we observe a variation in their distribution in the 17 programmes. According to *Table 6*, the percentage of total number of modules that self-assessed with 0 (as “not contributing to the programme outcome”) ranges from 0% to 58%, while the percentage of total number of modules that self-assessed with 4 (as making a “fairly strong contribution, with significant assessment relating to the programme outcome”) ranges from 0% to 30%.

When considering the distribution of self-assessment scores of 0 and 4, we can notice a significant variation among the programmes in the delivery of the ethics outcome. Turning our attention to the percentage of modules within a programme self-assessed with a score of 0, we notice two programmes that reported that more than half of their modules do not contribute to outcome e, followed closely by three programmes for which more than 40% of their modules received the score 0. At the other end we have five programmes for which less than 20% of the modules have no contribution to outcome e. Turning to the percentage of modules self-assessed with the score 4, nine programmes have deemed that less than 10% of their modules have a strong contribution to outcome e, while three programmes recorded a strong contribution to outcome e for 10-19% of their modules, and five programmes recorded a strong contribution to outcome e for more than 20% of their modules, with a maximum recorded of 30%:

Table 6. Distribution across programme for modules' scores for outcome e (n=17)

Table 6 shows a variation among the participant programmes in their delivery method of ethics education. There are two main methods of delivering ethics education in engineering programmes: in standalone modules dedicated to ethics or across the curriculum, with ethics permeating technical as well as non-technical modules. A high percentage of modules self-assessed a score of 0 and 1, with only a few modules deemed to have a strong contribution to outcome e, can be interpreted as suggesting a method of delivery of ethics education in standalone modules, while an even percentage of modules for each score would point to a method of ethics delivery envisioned to be across the curriculum. Six programmes mention explicitly in the programme description that they aim to deliver ethics across the curriculum, but in some cases the POLO scores seem to contradict this statement. For example, in one of the programmes that explicitly mentions an integration of ethics across the curriculum, almost half (46%) of modules score 0 for outcome e, while 33% of its modules have a score of 1.

4 SIGNIFICANCE

The study identifies major features of the current landscape of engineering ethics education. Given the limited empirical research on the implementation of ethics education in engineering programmes, the paper provides a unique insight into the provision of ethics education in Engineering programmes in a European setting. The findings can be of benefit to programme chairs, serving as guidance in the provision of ethics education in their own programmes, as well as to accreditation bodies in their

effort to ensure that all accreditation outcomes are on the same par in regards to their implementation. The present findings are part of a wider research study which examines in depth, through participant observation at accreditation events and interviews with engineering lecturers and accreditation evaluators, the coverage of ethics education, the experience and challenges encountered in the preparation of documentation submitted for accreditation and the evaluation for accreditation of the ethics outcome.

5 CONCLUSION

The study reveals that ethics, alongside other non-technical skills, is given less weight in the curricula of engineering programmes in Ireland, showing a still persistent division between traditional technically oriented engineering education and the contemporary calls for a hybrid socially oriented engineering education. The study also notes the lack of uniformity in the programmes' provision of ethics education and self-assessment of programme outcomes, leading to further questions as to how the programmes are assessed and deemed to have met by accreditation evaluators the ethics criterion.

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